

Provenance consumption

In this document we present several Why (Deep/Shallow), How, Where, and When-provenance questions we have asked ourselves regarding the provenance obtained from the application of the PROV-IDEA approach to a concrete *running example*.

More specifically, let us suppose a fictitious software company which has two concrete subsidiaries (*Sub_A* and *Sub_B*) and, for both business and strategic reasons, one of the subsidiaries (*Sub_A*) absorbs the other (*Sub_B*). In this situation, the company decides to merge the developers of both subsidiaries (`developer_sub_A` and `developer_sub_B`) into a single table of developers (`developer_sub_A_new`), but it also wants to keep the developers table of the absorbed subsidiary (`developer_sub_B_old`) for historical reasons. Considering that the semantics of the MERGE TABLE SMO involves deleting the source tables, first, table `developer_sub_B` is copied into table `developer_sub_B_old` (line 1, `COPY TABLE SMO`). Once this operator has been performed, both source tables are merged into the new one `developer_sub_A_new` (line 2, `MERGE TABLE SMO`). Finally, for optimal querying, the company decides to extract from the target table `developer_sub_A_new` the data referring to developers' contact form and performs a DECOMPOSE TABLE SMO (line 3).

```
1 COPY TABLE developer_sub_B INTO developer_sub_B_old
2 MERGE TABLE developer_sub_A, developer_sub_B INTO developer_sub_A_new
3 DECOMPOSE TABLE developer_sub_A_new INTO developer_sub_A (id, name, surname,...),
                                     contact (id, email,...)
```

The bindings, generated as TURTLE format files while performing these evolution changes, have been transformed into PROV documents (also in TURTLE format) using the *PROV-IDEA Expander [Expa]*. Later, these documents have been analyzed using the *PROV-IDEA Provenance Inspector [Insp]* aimed at answering the established questions.

Those questions have been defined by using different SPARQL query forms, that is, SELECT, DESCRIBE, CONSTRUCT and ASK [Sparql]. In particular, some of such questions have been answered using more than one SPARQL query form. In those cases, we have identified the different alternatives by:

- Question X-a (when using DESCRIBE),
- Question X-b (when using SELECT), and, when applicable,
- Question X-c (for CONSTRUCT).

Question 1a-WHY. What is the **description** of the last SMO used to generate a concrete surname value (in the query, the "ZaccheriaSN" surname) of a developer included in table `developer_sub_a` and the user who has executed such an operation?

File: 1questionDescribeSelectConstructWhySurnameGeneration.txt

Query: Why Deep-provenance

```
describe ?smo ?user
WHERE {
    exe:developer_sub_a sch2p:tableName ?a.
    exe:developer_sub_a prov:hadMember ?targetColumn.
    ?targetColumnValue prov:specializationOf ?targetColumn.
    ?targetColumn sch2p:columnName "surname".
    ?targetColumnValue prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smo.
    ?smo prov:wasAssociatedWith ?user.
    ?targetColumnValue d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
    ?targetColumnValue bitemp:startTransTime ?start1.
    filter not exists {
        ?targetColumnValue2 d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
        ?targetColumnValue2 bitemp:startTransTime ?start2.
        filter (?start2 > ?start1)
    }
}
```

Text result

```
exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652601Insert1
a "insert";
a prov:Activity;
bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.013"^^xsd:dateTime;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:47.131"^^xsd:dateTime;
o2p:executed "true";
o2p:instruction "insert INTO developer_sub_a select id, name, surname from developer_sub_a_new;";
prov:used exe:IdColumnValue_7_2_developer_sub_a_new_name,
exe:IdColumnValue_10_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname,
exe:IdColumnValue_4_2_developer_sub_a_new_id,
exe:IdColumnValue_3_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname,
exe:IdColumnValue_4_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname,
exe:IdColumnValue_7_2_developer_sub_a_new_id,
exe:IdColumnValue_10_2_developer_sub_a_new_name,
exe:IdColumn_3_developer_sub_a_id,
exe:IdColumnValue_10_2_developer_sub_a_new_id,
exe:IdColumnValue_6_2_developer_sub_a_new_id,
exe:IdColumnValue_1_2_developer_sub_a_new_name,
exe:IdColumnValue_9_2_developer_sub_a_new_id,
exe:IdColumnValue_6_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname,
exe:IdColumnValue_4_2_developer_sub_a_new_name,
exe:IdColumnValue_9_2_developer_sub_a_new_name,
exe:IdColumn_3_developer_sub_a_name,
exe:IdColumnValue_5_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname,
exe:IdColumnValue_7_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname,
exe:IdColumnValue_8_2_developer_sub_a_new_name,
exe:developer_sub_a,
exe:IdColumnValue_1_2_developer_sub_a_new_id,
exe:IdColumnValue_5_2_developer_sub_a_new_name,
exe:IdColumnValue_8_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname,
exe:IdColumnValue_5_2_developer_sub_a_new_id,
exe:IdColumnValue_8_2_developer_sub_a_new_id,
exe:IdColumnValue_2_2_developer_sub_a_new_name,
exe:IdColumnValue_2_2_developer_sub_a_new_id,
exe:IdColumnValue_9_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname,
exe:IdColumnValue_6_2_developer_sub_a_new_name,
exe:IdColumnValue_2_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname,
exe:IdColumnValue_3_2_developer_sub_a_new_name,
exe:IdColumnValue_1_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname,
exe:IdColumn_3_developer_sub_a_surname,
exe:IdColumnValue_3_2_developer_sub_a_new_id;
prov:wasAssociatedWith exe:Michael.
```

```

exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605
  a      "DecomposeTable";
  a      prov:Activity;
  bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.417"^^xsd:dateTime;
  bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.080"^^xsd:dateTime;
  o2p:executed "true";
  o2p:instruction "DecomposeTable";
  prov:used    exe:Migrator-19347652607_1_surname,
              exe:developer_sub_a_new, exe:Migrator-19347652607_1_id,
              exe:Migrator-19347652607_1_developer_sub_a,
              exe:Migrator-19347652607_1_contact,
              exe:Migrator-19347652607_1_name;
  prov:wasAssociatedWith exe:Michael.

exe:Michael a  prov:Agent.

```

Graphical result

Comment: the result has so many elements that its representation in PROV does not fit on the page.

Query: Why Shallow-provenance

```

describe ?smo ?user
WHERE {
  exe:developer_sub_a sch2p:tableName ?a.
  exe:developer_sub_a prov:hadMember ?targetColumn.
  ?targetColumnValue prov:specializationOf ?targetColumn.
  ?targetColumnValue prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smo.
  ?targetColumnValue d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
  ?targetColumnValue bitemp:startTransTime ?start1.
  ?smo_dmo prov:wasInformedBy ?smo.
  ?smo prov:wasAssociatedWith ?user.
  filter not exists {
    ?targetColumnValue2 d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
    ?targetColumnValue2 bitemp:startTransTime ?start2.
    filter (?start2 > ?start1)
  }
}

```

Text result

```

exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605
  a      "DecomposeTable";
  a      prov:Activity;
  bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.417"^^xsd:dateTime;
  bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.080"^^xsd:dateTime;
  o2p:executed "true";
  o2p:instruction "DecomposeTable";
  prov:used    exe:Migrator-19347652607_1_surname,
              exe:developer_sub_a_new, exe:Migrator-19347652607_1_id,
              exe:Migrator-19347652607_1_developer_sub_a,
              exe:Migrator-19347652607_1_contact,
              exe:Migrator-19347652607_1_name;
  prov:wasAssociatedWith exe:Michael.

exe:Michael a  prov:Agent.

```

Graphical result

Question 1b-WHY. What was the last SMO used to generate a concrete surname value (in the query, the "ZaccheriaSN" surname) of a developer included in table `developer_sub_a` and the user who has executed such an operation?

File: 1questionDescribeSelectConstructWhySurnameGeneration.txt

Query: Why Deep-provenance

```

Select ?smo ?user
WHERE {
    exe:developer_sub_a sch2p:tableName ?a.
    exe:developer_sub_a prov:hadMember ?targetColumn.
    ?targetColumnValue prov:specializationOf ?targetColumn.
    ?targetColumn sch2p:columnName "surname".
    ?targetColumnValue prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smo.
    ?smo prov:wasAssociatedWith ?user.
    ?targetColumnValue d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
    ?targetColumnValue bitemp:startTransTime ?start1.
    filter not exists {
        ?targetColumnValue2 d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
        ?targetColumnValue2 bitemp:startTransTime ?start2.
        filter (?start2 > ?start1)
    }
}

```

Result

smo	user
<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652601Insert1>	<http://example.org/Michael>
<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605>	<http://example.org/Michael>

Comment: The result shows that such a surname value has been ultimately generated by the Decompose Table SMO with identifier 19347652605 (*more specifically, by its suboperation Insert with identifier 19347652601Insert1*). As expected, the user who executed the operations is the same.

Query: Why Shallow-provenance

```

Select distinct ?smo ?user
WHERE {
    exe:developer_sub_a sch2p:tableName ?a.
    exe:developer_sub_a prov:hadMember ?targetColumn.
    ?targetColumnValue prov:specializationOf ?targetColumn.
    ?targetColumn sch2p:columnName "surname".
    ?targetColumnValue prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smo.
    ?targetColumnValue d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
    ?targetColumnValue bitemp:startTransTime ?start1.
    ?smo_dmo prov:wasInformedBy ?smo.
    ?smo prov:wasAssociatedWith ?user.
    filter not exists {
        ?targetColumnValue2 d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
        ?targetColumnValue2 bitemp:startTransTime ?start2.
        filter (?start2 > ?start1)
    }
}

```

Result

smo	user
<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605>	<http://example.org/AL>

Question 1c-WHY. What are the **main characteristics** of both the last SMO used to generate a concrete surname value (in the query, the "ZaccheriaSN" surname) of a developer included in table `developer_sub_a` and the user who has executed such an operation?

File: 1questionDescribeSelectConstructWhySurnameGeneration.txt

Query: Why Deep-provenance

```
construct {
  ?smo a prov:Activity .
  ?smo o2p:instruction ?instruc.
  ?smo o2p:executed ?executed.
  ?smo bitemp:startTransTime ?start.
  ?smo bitemp:endTransTime ?end.
  ?smo prov:wasAssociatedWith ?user.
  ?user a prov:Agent .
}
WHERE {
  exe:developer_sub_a sch2p:tableName ?a.
  exe:developer_sub_a prov:hadMember ?targetColumn.
  ?targetColumnValue prov:specializationOf ?targetColumn.
  ?targetColumnValue prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smo.
  ?targetColumnValue d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
  ?targetColumnValue bitemp:startTransTime ?start1.
  ?smo prov:wasAssociatedWith ?user.
  filter not exists {
    ?targetColumnValue2 d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
    ?targetColumnValue2 bitemp:startTransTime ?start2.
    filter (?start2 > ?start1).
  }
  ?smo a prov:Activity .
  ?smo o2p:instruction ?instruc.
  ?smo o2p:executed ?executed.
  ?smo bitemp:startTransTime ?start.
  ?smo bitemp:endTransTime ?end.
  ?smo prov:wasAssociatedWith ?user.
}
```

Text result

exe:Michael a prov:Agent .

exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605

```
a          prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime  "2024-06-24T16:03:48.417"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.080"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed        "true";
o2p:instruction      "DecomposeTable";
prov:wasAssociatedWith exe:Michael .
```

exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Insert1

```
a          prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime  "2024-06-24T16:03:48.013"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:47.131"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed        "true";
o2p:instruction      "insert INTO developer_sub_a select id, name, surname from developer_sub_a_new;";
prov:wasAssociatedWith exe:Michael .
```

Graphical result

Comment: the result has just the main attributes of the involved operators (the DECOMPOSE Table SMO and its associated INSERT DMO), including their relation with the user who executed the operation. That is, the associated SMO/DMO PROV elements and the user PROV element are shown, excluding their association with other elements.

Query: Why Shallow-provenance

```
construct {
    ?smo a prov:Activity .
    ?smo o2p:instruction ?instruc.
    ?smo o2p:executed ?executed.
    ?smo bitemp:startTransTime ?start.
    ?smo bitemp:endTransTime ?end.
    ?smo prov:wasAssociatedWith ?user.
    ?user a prov:Agent .
}
WHERE {
    exe:developer_sub_a sch2p:tableName ?a.
    exe:developer_sub_a prov:hadMember ?targetColumn.
    ?targetColumnValue prov:specializationOf ?targetColumn.
    ?targetColumnValue prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smo.
    ?targetColumnValue d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
    ?targetColumnValue bitemp:startTransTime ?start1.
    ?smo_dmo prov:wasInformedBy ?smo.
    filter not exists {
        ?targetColumnValue2 d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
        ?targetColumnValue2 bitemp:startTransTime ?start2.
        filter (?start2 > ?start1).
    }
    ?smo a prov:Activity .
    ?smo o2p:instruction ?instruc.
    ?smo o2p:executed ?executed.
    ?smo bitemp:startTransTime ?start.
    ?smo bitemp:endTransTime ?end.
    ?smo prov:wasAssociatedWith ?user.
}
```

Text result

exe:Michael a prov:Agent .

exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605

```
a                prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.417"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.080"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed      "true" ;
o2p:instruction    "DecomposeTable" ;
prov:wasAssociatedWith exe:Michael .
```

Graphical result

Question 2-WHERE. Which is the **description** of the database schema to which a particular surname value (in the query, the surname "ZaccheriaSN") in the developer_sub_a table belonged when it was ultimately created?

File: 2questionDescribeSelectWhereSurnameGeneration.txt

Query:

```
describe ?schema
WHERE {
  ex:developer_sub_a sch2p:tableName ?a.
  ex:developer_sub_a prov:hadMember ?targetColumn.
  ?targetColumnValue prov:specializationOf ?targetColumn.
  ?targetColumn sch2p:columnName "surname".
  ?targetColumnValue prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smo.
  ?targetColumnValue d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
  ?targetColumnValue bitemp:startTransTime ?start1.
  ?schema a prov:Entity , sch2p:schema.
  ?schema sch2p:schemaName ?schemaName.
  ?schema prov:hadMember ex:developer_sub_a.
  ?schema prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smo.
  filter not exists {
    ?targetColumnValue2 d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
    ?targetColumnValue2 bitemp:startTransTime ?start2.
    filter (?start2 > ?start1)
  }
}
```

Text result

```
exe:3c6daa2c96 a prov:Entity , sch2p:schema ;
bitemp:startTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.083"^^xsd:dateTime , "2024-06-24T16:03:48.363"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.082"^^xsd:dateTime ;
sch2p:schemaName "db_new" ;
prov:hadMember ex:developer_sub_b_old ,
ex:developer_sub_a ,
ex:developer_sub_a_new , exe:contact ;
prov:wasDerivedFrom ex:47d4d23c6e , exe:7f988b71a1 ;
prov:wasGeneratedBy ex:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Create2 ,
ex:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Drop ,
ex:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605 .
```

Graphical result

Question 2b-WHERE. Which is the database schema to which a particular surname value (in the query, the surname "ZaccheriaSN") in the developer_sub_a table belonged when it was ultimately created?

File: 2questionDescribeSelectWhereSurnameGeneration.txt

Query:

```
Select ?schema ?schemaName
WHERE {
    exe:developer_sub_a sch2p:tableName ?a.
    exe:developer_sub_a prov:hadMember ?targetColumn.
    ?targetColumnValue prov:specializationOf ?targetColumn.
    ?targetColumn sch2p:columnName "surname".
    ?targetColumnValue prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smo.
    ?targetColumnValue d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
    ?targetColumnValue bitemp:startTransTime ?start1.
    ?schema a prov:Entity , sch2p:schema.
    ?schema sch2p:schemaName ?schemaName.
    ?schema prov:hadMember exe:developer_sub_a.
    ?schema prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smo.
    filter not exists {
        ?targetColumnValue2 d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
        ?targetColumnValue2 bitemp:startTransTime ?start2.
        filter (?start2 > ?start1)
    }
}
```

Result

```
-----
| schema                               | schemaName |
=====
| <http://example.org/3c6daa2c96>    | "db_new"   |
-----
```

Question 3-WHEN. When does a particular surname value (in the query, the surname "ZaccheriaSN") in the developer_sub_a table was ultimately created?

File: 3questionSelectWhenSurnameGeneration.txt

Query:

```
Select distinct (?start1 as ?CreationTime)
WHERE {
  exe:developer_sub_a sch2p:tableName ?a.
  exe:developer_sub_a prov:hadMember ?targetColumn.
  ?targetColumnValue prov:specializationOf ?targetColumn.
  ?targetColumn sch2p:columnName "surname".
  ?targetColumnValue prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smo.
  ?targetColumnValue d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
  ?targetColumnValue bitemp:startTransTime ?start1.
  ?schema a prov:Entity , sch2p:schema.
  ?schema sch2p:schemaName ?schemaName.
  ?schema prov:hadMember exe:developer_sub_a.
  ?schema prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smo.
  filter not exists {
    ?targetColumnValue2 d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
    ?targetColumnValue2 bitemp:startTransTime ?start2.
    filter (?start2 > ?start1)
  }
}
```

Result

```
-----
| CreationTime |
-----
| "2024-06-24T16:03:48.253"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime> |
-----
```

Question 4-HOW. Which were the modifications performed in the database elements to obtain a concrete surname value (in the query, the "ZaccheriaSN" surname) of a developer registered in table `developer_sub_a` when it was ultimately created?

File: `4questionSelectHowSurnameGeneration.txt`

Query:

```

SELECT * WHERE{
  {
    SELECT distinct ?input ?smoType WHERE {
      exe:developer_sub_a sch2p:tableName ?a.
      exe:developer_sub_a prov:hadMember ?targetColumn.
      ?targetColumnValue prov:specializationOf ?targetColumn.
      ?targetColumn sch2p:columnName "surname".
      ?targetColumnValue prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smoType.
      ?targetColumnValue d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
      ?targetColumnValue bitemp:startTransTime ?start.
      ?targetColumnValue prov:wasDerivedFrom ?input.
      filter not exists {
        ?targetColumnValue2 d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
        ?targetColumnValue2 bitemp:startTransTime ?start2.
        filter (?start2 > ?start)
      }
    }
  }
}
union
{
  SELECT distinct ?input ?smoType WHERE{
    {
      SELECT distinct ?input2 WHERE {
        exe:developer_sub_a sch2p:tableName ?a.
        exe:developer_sub_a prov:hadMember ?targetColumn.
        ?targetColumnValue prov:specializationOf ?targetColumn.
        ?targetColumn sch2p:columnName "surname".
        ?targetColumnValue d2p:columnValue "ZaccheriaSN".
        ?targetColumnValue bitemp:startTransTime ?start1.
        ?targetColumnValue prov:wasDerivedFrom ?input2.
        filter not exists {
          ?targetColumnValue2 d2p:columnValue
"ZaccheriaSN".
          ?targetColumnValue2 bitemp:startTransTime ?start2.
          filter (?start2 > ?start1)
        }
      }
    }
    ?input2 prov:wasDerivedFrom+ ?input.
    ?input2 a prov:Entity , d2p:value.
    ?input2 prov:wasGeneratedBy ?smoType.
  }
}
}
}

```

Result

input	smoType
<http://example.org/IdColumnValue_6_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname>	<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652601Insert1>
<http://example.org/IdColumnValue_6_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname>	<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605>
<http://example.org/IdColumnValue_6_1_developer_sub_a_surname>	<http://example.org/MergeTableMigrator-14419536191Insert1>
<http://example.org/IdColumnValue_6_1_developer_sub_a_surname>	<http://example.org/MergeTableMigrator-14419536191>

Comment: as it can be inferred from the result, the concrete surname value "ZaccheriaSN" of the developer registered in table developer_sub_a, was ultimately created, after performing the operations:

- a Merge table SMO (in particular, after performing the corresponding Insert DMO suboperation). This operation used as input value the one identified as IdColumnValue_6_1_developer_sub_a_surname (taken from a previous version of table developer_sub_a, as the identifier states).
- The value identified as IdColumnValue_6_1_developer_sub_a_surname gave as a result, after the merge operation, the value identified as IdColumnValue_6_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname in table developer_sub_a_new.
- Finally, after performing a Decompose table SMO (and its corresponding Insert DMO suboperation), the value identified as IdColumnValue_6_2_developer_sub_a_new_surname results in the value "ZaccheriaSN", included as a surname of a developer in the last version of table developer_sub_a.

Question 5a-WHY. What is the **description** of the composite SMOs executed in the case study?

File: 5questionDescribeSelectComplexSMOSubSMODMO.txt

Query

```
describe ?SMO
WHERE {?SMO a prov:Activity.
       ?SMO_DMO prov:wasInformedBy ?SMO.
}
```

Text result

ex:CopyTableMigrator-8568938402

```
a          "CopyTable";
a          prov:Activity;
bitemp:endTransTime  "2024-06-24T12:37:42.802"^^xsd:dateTime;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T12:37:41.855"^^xsd:dateTime;
o2p:executed  "true";
o2p:instruction "CopyTable";
prov:used     ex:CopyTableMigrator-8568938402_1_developer_sub_b_old, ex:developer_sub_b;
prov:wasAssociatedWith ex:Olivia.
```

ex:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605

```
a          "DecomposeTable";
a          prov:Activity;
bitemp:endTransTime  "2024-06-24T16:03:48.417"^^xsd:dateTime;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.080"^^xsd:dateTime;
o2p:executed  "true";
o2p:instruction "DecomposeTable";
prov:used     ex:Migrator-19347652607_1_surname, ex:developer_sub_a_new, ex:Migrator-19347652607_1_id, ex:Migrator-19347652607_1_developer_sub_a, ex:Migrator-19347652607_1_contact, ex:Migrator-19347652607_1_name;
prov:wasAssociatedWith ex:Michael.
```

ex:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191

```
a          "MergeTable";
a          prov:Activity;
bitemp:endTransTime  "2024-06-24T12:46:06.791"^^xsd:dateTime;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T12:46:05.546"^^xsd:dateTime;
o2p:executed  "true";
o2p:instruction "MergeTable";
prov:used     ex:Migrator-14419536194_1_developer_sub_a_new, ex:developer_sub_a, ex:developer_sub_b;
prov:wasAssociatedWith ex:Mary.
```

Graphical result

Question 5b-WHY. What are the composite SMOs, together with their corresponding suboperators SMOs/DMOs executed in the case study?

File: 5questionDescribeSelectComplexSMOSubSMODMO.txt

Query

```
Select distinct ?Complex_SMO ?SMO_DMO
WHERE {
    ?SMO_DMO prov:wasInformedBy ?Complex_SMO.
} order by ?Complex_SMO
```

Result

Complex_SMO	SMO_DMO
<http://example.org/CopyTableMigrator-8568938402>	<http://example.org/CopyTableMigrator-8568938402Create>
<http://example.org/CopyTableMigrator-8568938402>	<http://example.org/CopyTableMigrator-8568938402Insert1>
<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605>	<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Create1>
<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605>	<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Create2>
<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605>	<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Drop>
<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605>	<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Insert1>
<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605>	<http://example.org/DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Insert2>
<http://example.org/MergeTableMigrator-14419536191>	<http://example.org/MergeTableMigrator-14419536191Create>
<http://example.org/MergeTableMigrator-14419536191>	<http://example.org/MergeTableMigrator-14419536191Drop1>
<http://example.org/MergeTableMigrator-14419536191>	<http://example.org/MergeTableMigrator-14419536191Drop2>
<http://example.org/MergeTableMigrator-14419536191>	<http://example.org/MergeTableMigrator-14419536191Insert>

Question 6a-WHY and HOW. What is the **description** of the tables that have been invalidated by the execution of the SMOs performed by a user (“Mary” in the query)?

File: 6questionDescribeSelectInvalidatedTables.txt

Query

```
describe ?table
WHERE {?table a sch2p:table , prov:Entity.
      ?table prov:wasInvalidatedBy ?smo.
      ?smo prov:wasAssociatedWith exe:Mary
}
```

Text result

```
exe:developer_sub_b a sch2p:table , prov:Entity ;
  bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T12:46:06.743"^^xsd:dateTime , "2024-06-24T12:46:06.427"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  sch2p:tableName "developer_sub_b" ;
  prov:wasInvalidatedBy exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191Drop2 , exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191 .

exe:developer_sub_a a sch2p:table , prov:Entity ;
  bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T12:46:06.601"^^xsd:dateTime , "2024-06-24T12:46:06.427"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.081"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  sch2p:tableName "developer_sub_a" ;
  prov:hadMember exe:ldColumn_3_developer_sub_a_id ,
    exe:ldColumn_3_developer_sub_a_name ,
    exe:ldColumn_3_developer_sub_a_surname ,
    exe:ldColumn_3_contact_id ,
    exe:ldColumn_3_contact_email ;
  prov:wasDerivedFrom exe:developer_sub_a_new ,
    exe:Migrator-19347652607_1_contact ,
    exe:Migrator-19347652607_1_developer_sub_a ;
  prov:wasGeneratedBy exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605 ,
    exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Create1 ;
  prov:wasInvalidatedBy exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191 ,
    exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191Drop1 .
```

Comment: as it can be inferred from the result, table **developer_sub_b** has been invalidated by a Merge Table SMO (and thus, by its suboperation Drop table). The timestamp registering the end transaction time is also shown (we note that the start transaction time is not included in the result since the PROVIDEA approach was applied to the case study to a database with the table **developer_sub_b** already created). A table with name **developer_sub_a**, on his part, has been involved on the execution of two different SMOs. On the one hand, such a table has been invalidated by a Merge Table SMO (and thus, by its suboperation Drop table). On the other hand, a table with the same name has been generated by the application of a Decompose Table SMO (and thus, by its suboperation Create table). Timestamps regarding the end transaction time (related to the deletion or invalidation of the table resulted from the Merge table-Drop table SMOs) and the start transaction time (related to the subsequent creation of the table resulted from the Decompose table-Create table SMOs) are also shown in the result.

Graphical result

Question 6b- WHY and HOW. What have been the tables that have been invalidated by the execution of the SMOs performed by a user (“Mary” in the query)?

File: 6questionDescribeSelectInvalidatedTables.txt

Query

```
Select distinct ?table
WHERE {?table sch2p:tableName ?a.
       ?table prov:wasInvalidatedBy ?smo.
       ?smo prov:wasAssociatedWith exe:Mary}
```

Result

```
-----
| table |
=====
| <http://example.org/developer_sub_b> |
| <http://example.org/developer_sub_a> |
-----
```

Question 7-WHY. What are the **main aspects** of the SMOs/DMOs executed and their relations?

File: 7questionConstructSMOsDMOs.txt

Query

```
construct {
  ?smo a prov:Activity.
  ?smo o2p:instruction ?instruct.
  ?smo o2p:executed ?executed.
  ?smo bitemp:startTransTime ?start.
  ?smo bitemp:endTransTime ?end.
  ?smo_dmo prov:wasInformedBy ?smo.
}
WHERE {
  ?smo a prov:Activity .
  ?smo o2p:instruction ?instruct.
  ?smo o2p:executed ?executed.
  ?smo bitemp:startTransTime ?start.
  ?smo bitemp:endTransTime ?end.
  ?smo prov:wasAssociatedWith ?user.
  optional{?smo_dmo prov:wasInformedBy ?smo.}
}
```

Text result

exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191Create

```
a          prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime  "2024-06-24T12:46:06.425"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T12:46:06.416"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed        "true" ;
o2p:instruction      "CreateTable" ;
prov:wasInformedBy  exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191 .
```

exe:CopyTableMigrator-8568938402

```
a          prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime  "2024-06-24T12:37:42.802"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T12:37:41.855"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed        "true" ;
o2p:instruction      "CopyTable" .
```

exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Create2

```
a          prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime  "2024-06-24T16:03:48.082"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.082"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed        "true" ;
o2p:instruction      "CreateTable" ;
prov:wasInformedBy  exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605 .
```

exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191Drop2

```
a          prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime  "2024-06-24T12:46:06.790"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T12:46:06.743"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed        "true" ;
o2p:instruction      "DropTable" ;
prov:wasInformedBy  exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191 .
```

exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Insert2

```
a          prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime  "2024-06-24T16:03:49.119"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:49.055"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed        "true" ;
o2p:instruction      "insert INTO contact select id, email from developer_sub_a_new;" ;
prov:wasInformedBy  exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605 .
```

exe:CopyTableMigrator-8568938402Create

```
a          prov:Activity ;
```

bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T12:37:42.723"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T12:37:42.715"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed "true";
o2p:instruction "CreateTable";
prov:wasInformedBy exe:CopyTableMigrator-8568938402 .

exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191Insert1

a prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T12:46:07.411"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T12:46:07.352"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed "true";
o2p:instruction "insert INTO developer_sub_a_new (select * from developer_sub_a union select * from developer_sub_b);";
prov:wasInformedBy exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191 .

exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605

a prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.417"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.080"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed "true";
o2p:instruction "DecomposeTable" .

exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Create1

a prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.081"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.080"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed "true";
o2p:instruction "CreateTable";
prov:wasInformedBy exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605 .

exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191

a prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T12:46:06.791"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T12:46:05.546"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed "true";
o2p:instruction "MergeTable" .

exe:CopyTableMigrator-8568938402Insert1

a prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T12:37:43.542"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T12:37:43.491"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed "true";
o2p:instruction "insert INTO developer_sub_b_old select * from developer_sub_b;";
prov:wasInformedBy exe:CopyTableMigrator-8568938402 .

exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191Drop1

a prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T12:46:06.670"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T12:46:06.601"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed "true";
o2p:instruction "DropTable";
prov:wasInformedBy exe:MergeTableMigrator-14419536191 .

exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Drop

a prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.417"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.363"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed "true";
o2p:instruction "DropTable";
prov:wasInformedBy exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605 .

exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605Insert1

a prov:Activity ;
bitemp:endTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:48.013"^^xsd:dateTime ;
bitemp:startTransTime "2024-06-24T16:03:47.131"^^xsd:dateTime ;
o2p:executed "true";
o2p:instruction "insert INTO developer_sub_a select id, name, surname from developer_sub_a_new;";
prov:wasInformedBy exe:DecomposeTableMigrator-19347652605 .

Graphical result

Question 8-WHY and WHEN. What is the **description** of the **SMOs** that have been carried out between two dates?

File: 8questionAskSMOTable.txt

Query

```
describe ?SMO
WHERE {
  ?SMO a prov:Activity.
  ?SMO_DMO prov:wasInformedBy ?SMO.
  ?SMO bitemp:startTransTime ?start.
FILTER(
  ?start >= xsd:date("2024-06-01")  &&
  ?start <=  xsd:date("2024-06-25")
)
}
```

Question 9-WHY. has the table `exe:developer_sub_a_new` been used as the input of an operation?

File: 9questionAskSMOTable.txt

Query

```
ask
WHERE {
  exe:developer_sub_a_new sch2p:tableName ?a.
  ?smo prov:used  exe:developer_sub_a.
}
```

Graphical result

References

[Sparql] SPARQL 1.1 Query Language. Available at <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/>.

[Expa] PROV-IDEA Expander. Online at <https://github.com/PROV-IDEA/PROV-IDEA-Expander/>.

[Insp] PROV-IDEA Provenance Inspector. Online at <https://github.com/PROV-IDEA/PROV-IDEA-Provenance-Inspector/>.